

Synthesis, characterization, molecular docking, ADME study, and antimicrobial evaluation of new fenamate-isatin hybrids

Lubna Layth Taha¹

¹ Department of Health in Diyala, Ministry of Health and Environments, Diyala, Iraq

² Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq

Corresponding author: Lubna Layth Taha (lobna.taha2200m@copharm.uobaghdad.edu.iq)

Received 20 December 2024 ♦ Accepted 22 January 2025 ♦ Published 28 February 2025

Citation: Taha LL, Al-Mudhafar MMJ (2025) Synthesis, characterization, molecular docking, ADME study, and antimicrobial evaluation of new fenamate-isatin hybrids. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e143889>

Abstract

Molecular hybridization produced six new derivatives by combining isatin analogues with two fenamic acid derivatives. These compounds were characterized using FT-IR and ¹H-NMR and tested for antimicrobial activity. Most of these compounds show potent activity compared to ciprofloxacin against gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and *Bacillus subtilis*) and gram-negative (*Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Escherichia coli*). Additionally, they demonstrated a higher antifungal activity than fluconazole against *Candida albicans*. A molecular docking study was performed for all six hybrids with three proteins: *E. coli* DNA Gyrase B (PDB: 6H86), *S. aureus* (PDB: 2W9H), and CYP51 (PDB: 4WMZ). The results showed promising inhibition of the bacterial and fungal proteins. Furthermore, the ADME study predicted favorable drug-like properties for these compounds.

Keywords

antimicrobial activity, fenamates, hydrazide, isatin, molecular docking

Introduction

When pharmacophores' moieties of various biologically active compounds are combined, a new hybrid molecule with better affinity and efficacy than the parent medications is created. This combination may lead to distinct or dual modes of action and fewer undesirable side effects (Al-Mudhafar and Wadi 2024).

Scientists are particularly interested in isatin among the various nitrogen-containing heterocycles because of its many beneficial qualities. Isatin, chemically named 1H-indole-2,3-dione, is a naturally occurring substance discovered in the early 19th century as an oxidized form of indole. It has been recognized for an extensive spectrum of biological ac-

tivities, along with its analogues, which are important chemical groups with significant applications in medicinal chemistry. Isatin serves as the core structure for numerous bioactive derivatives with various and valuable biological activities including antibacterial (Shakir and Al-Mudhafar 2020; Mukhlif and Al-Mudhafar 2023a; Al-Musawi and Al-Mudhafar 2024; Hamza and Al-Mudhafar 2024) anti-HIV (Selvam et al. 2001), antitubercular (Gao et al. 2019), anti-inflammatory (Zeeshan et al. 2019), anticancer (Abo-Salem et al. 2020), antioxidant (Al-Mudhafar and Wadi 2024), anticonvulsant (Khajouei et al. 2018), and central nervous system depressive effects (Zhen et al. 2015; Kamoon et al. 2020).

Because of their diverse chemical characteristics, isatin-based compounds (Fig. 1) can be utilized as reactants

to create a wide range of physiologically active products (Abdulkadir et al. 2022). Particularly, the keto (C=O) group at position 3 and the amide (C=O) group at position 2 are capable of taking part in the condensation and addition processes. Besides, substituents at these two positions have been found to play an important role in modulating their anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial activities (Jarapula et al. 2016; Mohammed and Leelon 2021).

Isatin	X=H
5-Fluoroisatin	X=F
5-Bromoisatin	X=Br

Figure 1. Chemical structure of Isatin and its analogues.

Hydrazides represent an important class of organic compounds defined by the presence of a nitrogen–nitrogen covalent bond attached to a carbonyl group. These functional groups endow the pharmacophore with distinctive pharmacological activities, making hydrazides and their derivatives indispensable intermediates and pivotal starting materials for the development of novel bioactive compounds (Popiołek 2010; Sabzi and Al-Mudhafar 2023).

Almutairi et al. (2018) synthesized a new series of hydrazide-hybrid molecules by combining indole acetic acid and isatin compounds. These hybrids were tested for antimicrobial activity against a range of pathogens, including Gram-positive bacteria (*Enterococcus fecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, MRSA, and *Bacillus subtilis*), Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Salmonella enteritidis*), and fungi (*Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, and *Penicillium notatum*). Among these hybrids, the compounds with halogen substitutions, specifically Cl and F, demonstrated the highest activity.

On the other hand, the most often used pharmaceuticals for anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic purposes are non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). NSAIDs work primarily as competitive inhibitors of cyclooxygenase enzymes (COX-1 and COX-2). Ismail et al. (2022) synthesized new derivatives of ibuprofen, one of the most commonly used NSAIDs, by conjugating it with isatin. These derivatives exhibited significant anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activities.

The fenamic acids, or fenamates, are an important class of NSAIDs, with four primary members widely used clinically: mefenamic acid, flufenamic acid, meclofenamic acid, and tolfenamic acid (Sharma and Prasher 2023). These fenamic acids have been used as precursors in synthesizing various compounds by incorporating them with heterocyclic. The resulting derivatives exhibit a wide range of therapeutic applications, including anticancer, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic activities (Sabah et al. 2020).

A major public health concern in recent years has been the rise in drug-resistant infectious illnesses brought on by bacterial infections. Furthermore, infections resulting from bacteria resistant to drugs pose a significant global health risk. Infections caused by the Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and species of the genus *Enterococcus* are of particular importance because of their propensity to develop antibiotic resistance to multiple antibiotics and their increasing incidence in hospitals and communities. This has prompted scientists and researchers to modify and create new, effective chemotherapeutic agents with antibacterial properties (El-Faham et al. 2015; Alzahrani et al. 2022; Hamza and Al-Mudhafar 2024).

Since the halogenated aromatic compounds have different biological activities, especially those with fluorine-containing organic compounds, in particular, demonstrate notable enhancements in pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties (Mukhlif and Al-Mudhafar 2023b). The researchers, in this study, hypothesized that combining two different halogenated fenamic acids, tolfenamic acid and flufenamic acid, with bioactive molecules of isatin analogues could yield new hybrid molecules with expected antimicrobial activity. Furthermore, molecular docking investigations were performed on the final hybrids (5–10) to find their ability to bind to and inhibit bacterial and fungal proteins. Also, an ADME study was performed for them.

Materials and methods

Materials

Tolfenamic acid, flufenamic acid, 5-fluoroisatin, and 5-bromoisatin were obtained from Maclin (China), while isatin was from Picasso-e (China). Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) with Silica gel GF254 (type 60) pre-coated aluminum sheets from Merck company (Germany) was used to follow up the reactions progress and the purity of compounds. UV-254 light was utilized to identify the spots. The solvent system that was adopted was ethyl acetate: hexane (1:1). The melting points were identified using Stuart's (SMP3) melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. The infrared spectra were obtained using a Fourier Transform Infrared (ν , cm^{-1}) spectrometer (Shimadzu, WQF-520/Japan) at the University of Baghdad/College of Pharmacy. The proton nuclear magnetic resonance ($^1\text{H-NMR}$) spectra were determined employing an NMR ultra-shield spectrophotometer 400 MHz, BRUKER (Iraq/at the University of Basra). The solvent utilized for sample analysis was DMSO-d₆.

Chemical synthesis

Synthesis of fenamic ethyl esters (2a and 2b)

Tolfenamic acid (1a, 11.5 mmol, 3 g) and flufenamic acid (1b, 10.6 mmol, 3 g) were each placed in separate round-bottom flasks and dissolved in approximately 50 mL of ethanol. Subsequently, 3 mL of H_2SO_4 was carefully added to each solution. Then the content of the flasks

was refluxed for 18 h, as shown in Scheme 1. The progression of the reactions was monitored using TLC. After finishing these reactions, the solvent was allowed to evaporate, and then the resulting precipitate was neutralized using Na₂CO₃ solution and filtered. Then the remaining precipitate was washed several times with water, collected, and recrystallized from ethanol (Alzahrani et al. 2022).

The synthesized compound of tolfenamic ethyl ester (2a) was obtained as white crystals with a melting point of 59 °C. Its FT-IR (ν , cm⁻¹) showed characteristic peaks: 3298.28 (N-H str.), 3082.25 (C-H, aromatic str.), 2978.09 (C-H, aliphatic str.), 1670.35 (C=O str. of carbonyl ester), 1581.63 and 1519.91 (aromatic, C=C, str.), and 1010.7 (C-O-C str.).

The flufenamic ethyl ester (2b) was obtained as a brown oily liquid. Its FT-IR (ν , cm⁻¹) displayed peaks at 3309.85 (N-H str.), 3074.02 (C-H, aromatic str.), 2981.95 (C-H, aliphatic str.), 1681.93 (C=O str. of carbonyl ester), 1581.63 and 1519.91 (aromatic, C=C, str.), and 1118.71 (C-O-C str.).

Synthesis of fenamic hydrazides (3a and 3b)

To a solution of fenamic ethyl esters (2a (10.3 mmol, 3 g) and 2b (10.3 mmol, 3.18 g)) in ethanol in separate round-bottom flasks, then an excess amount of hydrazine hydrate 80% (51.5 mmol, 1.65 g) was added dropwise. The reaction mixtures were refluxed for 12–18 h. After the completion of the reaction (indicated by TLC), the solvent was allowed to evaporate from the solid product, washed with cold water several times,

and then air dried, followed by recrystallization from 70% ethanol (Alzahrani et al. 2022).

The obtained compound of tolfenamic hydrazide (3a) was pale yellow crystals with a melting point of 138–139 °C. FT-IR (ν , cm⁻¹): 3325.28, 3305.99, and 3248.13 (N-H str.), 3074.53 and 3028.24 (C-H, aromatic str.), 2854.65 (C-H, aliphatic str.), 1620.21 (C=O str. of carbonyl amide), 1592.0 and 1508.33 (aromatic, C=C, str.), 1014.56 (C-O-C str.). Meanwhile, the flufenamic hydrazide (3b) was obtained as pale-yellow crystals with a melting point of 137–138 °C. FT-IR (ν , cm⁻¹): 3290.56, 3259.70, and 3197.98 (N-H str.), 2985.81 (C-H, aromatic str.), 1678.07 (C=O str. of carbonyl amide), 1581.63 (aromatic, C=C, str.), 1111.01 (C-O-C str.).

Synthesis of tolfenamic-isatin hybrids

Isatin (1.019 mmol, 0.15 g), 5-fluoroisatin (1.017 mmol, 0.168 g), and 5-bromoisatin (1.017 mmol, 0.23 g) were each weighed and placed in separate round-bottom flasks. Each compound was dissolved in 25 mL of hot ethanol, followed by the addition of a few drops of glacial acetic acid to each flask. After stirring for 15 minutes, tolfenamic hydrazide (1.017 mmol, 0.28 g) was added to each solution, and the mixtures were refluxed for 12 h. The reaction progression was monitored using TLC and the conversion of the solution into suspension indicated the formation of the imine group (Hamza and Al-Mudhafar 2024). Then the products were filtered, washed with distilled water, and recrystallized from ethanol.

First step

Second step

Scheme 1. The chemical synthesis steps of the final hybrids and intermediates.

2-((3-chloro-2-methylphenyl)amino)-N'-(2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene) benzohydrazide (5)

Yellow crystals; Chemical Formula: $C_{22}H_{17}ClN_4O_2$, Molecular Weight: 404.85 g/mol, Rf = 0.8 (ethyl acetate: hexane (1:1)), M.P: 274–275 °C; yield 50%. FT-IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3298.28 (N-H str. of secondary amine), 3190.26 (N-H, str. of hydrazide), 2981.95 (C-H, aliphatic str.), 1724.36 (C=O str. carbonyl), 1670.35 (C=O str. of amide), 1581.63 (C=C str.), 1519.91 (C=N stretching vibration of imine). The 1H -NMR (δ =ppm): 13.96 (1H, s, N-H), 11.35 (1H, s, N-H of isatin), 9.23 (1H, s, N-H of tolfenamic acid), 7.69–6.79 (11H, s, Ar-H), 2.28 (3H, s, CH₃ of tolfenamic acid).

2-((3-chloro-2-methylphenyl)amino)-N'-(5-fluoro-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene) benzohydrazide (6)

Yellow crystals; Chemical Formula: $C_{22}H_{16}ClFN_4O_2$, Molecular Weight: 422.84 g/mol, Rf = 0.66 (ethyl acetate: hexane (1:1)), M.P: 296–297 °C; yield 50%. FT-IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3259.70 (N-H str. of secondary amine), 3059.10 (C-H, aromatic str.), 2920.23 (C-H, aliphatic str.), 1701.22 (C=O str. carbonyl), 1651.07 (C=O str. of amide), 1577.77 (C=C str.), 1531.48 (C=N stretching vibration of imine). The 1H -NMR (δ =ppm): 13.97 (1H, s, N-H), 11.38 (1H, s, N-H of isatin), 9.21 (1H, s, N-H of tolfenamic acid), 7.7–6.97 (10H, m, Ar-H), 2.28 (3H, s, CH₃ of tolfenamic acid).

2-(5-bromo-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene-2-((3-chloro-2-methylphenyl)amino) benzohydrazide (7)

Orange crystals; Chemical Formula: $C_{22}H_{16}BrClN_4O_2$, Molecular Weight: 483.75 g/mol, Rf = 0.6 (ethyl acetate: hexane (1:1)), M.P: 264–265 °C; yield 55%. FT-IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3201.83 (N-H str. of secondary amine), 3082.25 (C-H, aromatic str.), 2962.66 (C-H, aliphatic str.), 1701.22 (C=O str. carbonyl), 1651.07 (C=O str. of amide), 1581.63 (C=C str.), 1519.91 (C=N stretching vibration of imine). The 1H -NMR (δ =ppm): 13.9 (1H, s, N-H), 11.47 (1H, s, N-H of isatin), 9.19 (1H, s, N-H of tolfenamic acid), 7.67–6.92 (10H, m, Ar-H), 2.27 (3H, s, CH₃ of tolfenamic acid).

Synthesis of flufenamic-isatin hybrids

Isatin (1.019 mmol, 0.15 g), 5-fluoroisatin (1.017 mmol, 0.167 g), and 5-bromoisatin (1.017 mmol, 0.23 g) were each placed in separate boiling flasks, then dissolved in 25 mL hot ethanol, and a few drops of glacial acetic acid were added to each flask. After 15 min. (1.01 mmol, 0.3 g) of flufenamic hydrazide was added and then refluxed for 12 h. The reaction progression was monitored using TLC and the conversion of the solution into suspension indication of the formation of the imine group (Hamza and Al-Mudhafar 2024). Then the final products were filtered, washed with distilled water, and recrystallized from ethanol.

2-(2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene-2-((3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl) amino) benzohydrazide (8)

Yellow crystals; Chemical Formula: $C_{22}H_{15}F_3N_4O_2$, Molecular Weight: 424.38 g/mol, Rf = 0.7 (ethyl acetate: hexane (1:1)), M.P: 271–272 °C; yield 50%. FT-IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3259.70 (N-H str. secondary amine), 1697.36 (C=O str. of carbonyl), 1666.50 (C=O of amide), 1581.63 (C=C str.), 1527.62 (C=N str. of imine). The 1H -NMR (δ =ppm): 13.87 (1H, s, N-H), 11.3 (1H, s, N-H of isatin), 9.09 (1H, s, N-H of flufenamic acid), 7.75–6.92 (12H, m, Ar-H).

5-fluoro-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene-2-((3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) amino) benzohydrazide (9)

Orange crystals; Chemical Formula: $C_{22}H_{14}F_4N_4O_2$, Molecular Weight: 442.37 g/mol, Rf = 0.71 (ethyl acetate: hexane (1:1)), M.P: 280–281 °C; yield 50%. FT-IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3255.84 (N-H str. of secondary amine), 1697.36 (C=O str. carbonyl), 1658.78 (C=O str. of amide), 1581.63 (C=C str.), 1531.48 (C=N stretching vibration of imine). The 1H -NMR (δ =ppm): 13.85 (1H, s, N-H), 11.31 (1H, s, N-H of isatin), 9.06 (1H, s, N-H of flufenamic acid), 7.75–6.91 (11H, m, Ar-H).

5-bromo-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene-2-((3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) amino) benzohydrazide (10)

Orange crystals; Chemical Formula: $C_{22}H_{14}BrF_3N_4O_2$, Molecular Weight: 503.28 g/mol, Rf = 0.73 (ethyl acetate: hexane (1:1)), M.P: 239–240 °C; yield 60%. FT-IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3229.56 (N-H str. of secondary amine), 1697.36 (C=O str. carbonyl), 1651.07 (C=O str. of amide), 1573.91 (C=C str.), 1516.05 (C=N stretching vibration of imine). The 1H -NMR (δ =ppm): 13.78 (1H, s, N-H), 11.41 (1H, s, N-H of isatin), 9.05 (1H, s, N-H of flufenamic acid), 7.75–6.88 (11H, m, Ar-H).

Antimicrobial activity test

The agar well diffusion method was used to detect different antimicrobial activity of the final hybrids, the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), and the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) at Cac Company in Iraq. In vitro tests were used to determine the activity of the compounds against seven organisms. The Gram-positive bacteria were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and *Bacillus subtilis*, while the Gram-negative were *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Escherichia coli*, and against the fungi *Candida albicans*. The standard for Gram-positive and Gram-negative was ciprofloxacin; meanwhile, the standard for the fungi was fluconazole.

Molecular docking

Molecular docking studies were accomplished using the Glide tool in the Maestro platform 13.0.135 to evaluate the binding affinity of synthesized fenamate-isatin hybrids into the binding sites of the protein *S. aureus* (PDB ID: 2W9H) (Heaslet et al. 2009) and *E. coli* DNA Gyrase B (PDB ID: 6F86) (Naramore et al. 2019) and CYP51 (PDB ID: 4WMZ) (Sagatova et al. 2015). The proteins were prepared with the aid of the protein preparation workflow within Maestro software.

The receptor grid was created to bring about the boundary box of 12 Å x 12 Å x 12 Å in dimensions. The ligand structures were pulled using the 2D Sketcher within the Maestro program, along with employing LigPrep in the Maestro suite. The energy for the prepared ligands was minimized using the force field OPLS_2005 (Friesner et al. 2006; Harder et al. 2016). The prepared ligands were docked into the prepared compounds using Glide software in standard precision (SP) (Halgren et al. 2004; Ali and Al-Hamashi 2024).

ADME study

The pharmacological characteristics of the ligands conformed to Lipinski's rule of five, and the ADME parameters were computed using Schrodinger Maestro's Qik-Probe application. Lipinski's rule of five considers many molecular features, including the total count of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors (Chidambaram 2023). The primary objective of the study is to ascertain the most significant pharmacokinetic properties of the substances, encompassing their intestinal absorption, systemic distribution, hepatotoxicity, excretion, metabolism, water solubility, and additional ADME descriptors.

Results and discussion

Chemistry

The fenamic acid derivatives (flufenamic and tolfenamic) were converted to their corresponding ethyl esters by refluxing with ethanol with the aid of H₂SO₄. Then hydrazine hydrate was employed to convert the above esters to the corresponding hydrazide. The synthesized hydrazides were formed by the acid-catalyzed reaction, where the amine nitrogen of the fenamic acid hydrazides attacked the carbon atom of the keto group in the isatin analogues. This nucleophilic attack leads to the formation of imine C=N, accompanied by water elimination.

The structures of the newly synthesized compounds were confirmed by FT-IR and ¹H-NMR analysis.

The IR spectrum showed the disappearance of the C=O stretching band in the isatin analogs (isatin: 1724 cm⁻¹, 5-fluoroisatin: 1732 cm⁻¹, and 5-bromoisatin: 1743 cm⁻¹), along with the appearance of a new band around 1519–1531 cm⁻¹ of the imine C=N stretching in the newly synthesized hydrazides (5–10). The ¹H-NMR shows three distinct peaks around 13.3–13.9 ppm, 11.3–11.47 ppm, and 9.05–6.23 ppm. Indicating the presence of three amine hydrogens (1H of the hydrazone, 1H of the isatin analogue, and 1H of the fenamic acid analogue), respectively.

Molecular docking

The docking scores of the synthesized compounds and the reference compounds are shown in Table 1. The two-dimensional (2D) interactions are illustrated in Fig. 2. The docking score shows comparable results of the synthesized compounds with the reference (fluconazole) regarding the protein 4WMZ. Meanwhile, the docking scores of bacterial proteins, 6F86 and 2W9H, show higher binding affinities for synthesized compounds than the reference compound, Ciprofloxacin. Specifically, for protein 6F86, compounds 5, 6, 8, and 9 show docking scores ranging between -6.376 and -5.435. Similarly, for protein 2W9H, compounds 5, 6, and 7 demonstrate docking scores ranging from -5.822 to -5.740. A more negative docking score indicates lower binding energy and higher affinity for the binding site, reflecting stronger interactions with the protein.

Table 1. Docking score of the final compounds against the references (ciprofloxacin and fluconazole).

Title	Docking Score kcal/mol		
	4WMZ	6F86	2W9H
5	-5.031	-5.435	-5.740
6	-6.038	-6.376	-5.772
7	-5.118	-4.872	-5.822
8	-3.499	-5.566	-4.946
9	-5.640	-6.131	-5.296
10	-5.424	-4.920	-5.258
Ciprofloxacin	—	-5.034	-5.337
Fluconazole	-6.184	—	—

6F86: Compound 6

Figure 2. Best docked ligands with 6F86, 2W9H, and 4WMZ.

6F86: Compound 9

6F86: Ciprofloxacin (Reference Compound)

2W9H: Compound 6

Figure 2. Continued.

The 4WMZ protein shows the same interactions for both the reference (fluconazole) and compound 6, represented by hydrogen bonding with TYR 140 and HEM 601 and good fitting in the hydrophobic pocket of the protein composed of (LEU 129, TYR 126, TYR 140, ILE 139, and VAL 311). Thus, the docking results were close and considered comparable. For protein 6H86, these interactions

include hydrogen bonding of the carbonyl group with ASP 73 and GLY 77 for compounds 5, 6, and 9 and the amine group with ASN 46 and the imine group with ASP 73 for compound 8. Also, pi-cation interaction with ARG 76 was found with compound 9, where these interactions were absent for ciprofloxacin, therefore contributing to higher binding affinity.

2W9H: Compound 7

2W9H: Ciprofloxacin (Reference Compound)

4WMZ: Compound 6

Figure 2. Continued.

As for the 2W9H protein, compounds 5, 6, and 7 show pi-pi stacking with PHE 92, a halogen bond with ASP 27, and hydrogen bonding of the carbonyl group with water, and all compounds (5, 6, and 7) are placed in the hydrophobic pocket formed by (PHE 92, LEU 28, VAL 31, PHE 98,

ALA 7, VAL 6, and LEU 5) and (LEU 28, VAL 31, ALA 7, VAL 6, LEU 5, PHE 98, PHE 92, and ILE 14) and (LEU 28, PHE 92, VAL 31, LEU 5, VAL 6, and VAL 7), respectively. All these interactions contribute to an increase in the binding affinity of the ligands with the protein.

Table 2. Predicted ADME data for the final hybrids and reference compounds.

Title	ciprofloxacin	fluconazole	5	6	7	8	9	10
QPPCaco	12.775	747.552	554.894	555.287	555.733	491.025	491.948	636.530
QPlogS	-3.794	-2.202	-7.376	-7.744	-8.246	-7.772	-8.149	-6.637
QPlogPo/w	0.281	0.514	5.524	5.760	6.101	5.773	6.014	5.675
accptHB	6.000	6.750	3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000
donorHB	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
RuleOf3	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
RuleOf5	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2
CNS	0	0	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	0
PercentHuman	48.392	81.385	95.445	96.836	100.000	95.958	100.000	84.443
OralAbsorption								

The standard criteria for the rule of five are molecular weight < 500, donor HB ≤ 5, acceptor HB ≤ 10, and QPlogPo/w < 5. Compounds that abide by these rules are regarded as drug-like. The rule of three includes the following: QPlogS > -5.7, QP PCaco > 22 nm/s, #metab < 7.

Compounds that have fewer violations of these rules are probably more orally available. Percent of human oral absorption: 48 for low, 76 for medium, or 100 for high. CNS Predicted central nervous system activity on a -2 (inactive, not entering the CNS) to +2 (active, entering the CNS) scale (Ali and Al-Hamashi 2024).

Table 3. Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) in mcg/mL of the fenamate-isatin hybrids against different microorganisms.

Isolates		Gram-positive			Gram-negative			Fungi
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>N. gonorrhoeae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
Compounds		Concentration (mcg/mL)						
5	MBC	256	256	256	256	256	256	512
	MIC	128	128	128	128	128	128	256
6	MBC	64	64	512	512	256	512	256
	MIC	32	32	256	256	128	256	128
7	MBC	64	256	256	256	512	256	256
	MIC	32	128	128	128	256	128	128
8	MBC	512	512	512	512	512	512	512
	MIC	256	256	256	256	256	256	256
9	MBC	256	256	256	65	256	256	256
	MIC	128	128	128	32	128	128	128
10	MBC	256	256	256	512	1024	512	256
	MIC	128	128	128	256	512	256	128
Ciprofloxacin*	MBC	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	MIC	1024	1024	1024	1024	1024	1024	—
Fluconazole**	MBC	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	MIC	—	—	—	—	—	—	1024

*Ciprofloxacin is the reference for antibacterial activity.

**Fluconazole is the reference for antifungal activity.

Table 4. Inhibition Zone (IZ) in mm of new fenamate-isatin hybrids at the MIC for different microorganisms.

Isolates	Inhibition Zone (IZ) in mm***						
	Gram-positive			Gram-negative			Fungi
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>N. gonorrhoeae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
5	25	30	23	20	25	25	22
6	26	25	25	22	28	24	23
7	20	25	26	19	26	23	19
8	27	23	25	22	25	20	23
9	29	25	25	20	26	21	27
10	23	19	24	17	21	18	15
DMSO	Zero	zero	zero	zero	zero	zero	zero
Ciprofloxacin*	29	25	30	24	25	28	—
Fluconazole**	—	—	—	—	—	—	25

*Ciprofloxacin is the reference for antibacterial activity.

**Fluconazole is the reference for antifungal activity.

*** (Zero) = without activity, mildly active (inhibition zone within 5 and 10 mm), moderately active (inhibition zone within 10 and 20 mm), and particularly active (inhibition zone more than 20 mm) (Sahib and Mohammed 2020).

especially for 5, 6, 8, and 9 for the 6F86 protein and 6, 7, and 8 for the 2W9H protein compared with ciprofloxacin. Meanwhile, the 4WMZ protein results were close and comparable with fluconazole. The ADME analysis indicates that these compounds are drug-like entities with a satisfactory pharmacokinetic profile. The findings of this study can be utilized to develop new bioactive fenamate-based antimicrobial compounds.

Acknowledgment

We sincerely appreciate the University of Baghdad's ongoing assistance.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

References

- Abdulkadir MQ, Abdulwahab AH, Al-Mudhafar MM (2022) Synthesis and evaluating the antimicrobial activities of various adducts prepared from isatins and proline. *International Journal of Drug Delivery Technology* 12(2): 682–687. <https://doi.org/10.25258/ijddt.12.2.38>
- Abo-Salem HM, Nassrallah A, Soliman AA, Ebied MS, Elawady ME, Abdelhamid SA, El-Sawy ER, Al-Sheikh YA, Aboul-Soud MA (2020) Synthesis and bioactivity assessment of novel spiro pyrazole-oxindole congeners exhibiting potent and selective in vitro anticancer effects. *Molecules* 25(5): 1124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25051124>
- Ali RM, Al-Hamashi AA (2024) Molecular docking, ADMET, molecular dynamic simulation, synthesis, and preliminary antiproliferative study of 1,2,4-thiadiazole derivatives as possible histone Deacetylase Inhibitors. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 23(7): 1301–1308. <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v23i7.X>
- Al-Mudhafar MM, Wadi JS (2024) Synthesis and biological activity evaluation of new isatin-gallate hybrids as antioxidant and anticancer agents (in vitro) and in silico study as anticancer agents and coronavirus inhibitors. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e124992>
- Al-Musawi MH, Al-Mudhafar MM (2024) Synthesis, characterization, molecular docking, ADMET study, and antimicrobial evaluation of new mannich bases of isatin–thiazole imine bases. *Al-Rafidain Journal of Medical Sciences* 6(2): 201–208. <http://doi.org/10.54133/ajms.v6i2.835>
- Almutairi MS, Zakaria AS, Ignasius PP, Al-Wabli RL, Joe IH, Attia MI (2018) Synthesis, spectroscopic investigations, DFT studies, molecular docking and antimicrobial potential of certain new indole-isatin molecular hybrids: experimental and theoretical approaches. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1153: 333–345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2017.10.025>
- The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.
- The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.
- The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.
- Funding**
No funding was reported.
- Author contributions**
The first author, Lubna, contributed to synthesizing the desired compounds, the analysis of IR and ¹H-NMR data, the discussion of antimicrobial activity, the preparation of the text, and its critical editing. The second author, May, performed the study's design, examined the final results, and approved the manuscript in its final form.
- Author ORCIDs**
Lubna Layth Taha <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7027-7806>
May Mohammed Jawad Al-Mudhafar <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9747-3140>
- Data availability**
All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
- Alzahrani A Y, Ammar Y A, Salem M A, Abu-Elghait M, Ragab A (2022) Design, synthesis, molecular modeling, and antimicrobial potential of novel 3-[(1H-pyrazol-3-yl) imino] indolin-2-one derivatives as DNA gyrase inhibitors. *Archiv der Pharmazie* 355(1): 2100266. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ardp.202100266>
- Castro-Alvarez A, Costa AM, Vilarrasa J (2017) The performance of several docking programs at reproducing protein-macrolide-like crystal structures. *Molecules* 22(1): 136. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22010136>
- Chidambaram K (2023) Identification of BACE-1 inhibitors against Alzheimer's disease through E-pharmacophore-based virtual screening and molecular dynamics simulation studies: An Insilco Approach. *Life* 13(4): 952. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life13040952>
- El-Faham A, Hozzein WN, Wadaan MAM, Khattab SN, Ghabbour HA, Fun HK, Siddiqui MR (2015) Microwave synthesis, characterization, and antimicrobial activity of some novel isatin derivatives. *Journal of Chemistry* 716987: 8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/716987>
- Friesner RA, Murphy RB, Repasky MP, Frye LL, Greenwood JR, Halgren TA, Sanschagrin PC, Mainz DT (2006) Extra precision glide: Docking and scoring incorporating a model of hydrophobic enclosure for protein–ligand complexes. *Journal of medicinal chemistry* 49(21): 6177–6196. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm051256o>
- Gao F, Chen Z, Ma L, Fan Y, Chen L, Lu G (2019) Synthesis and biological evaluation of moxifloxacin-acetyl-1, 2, 3-1H-triazole-methylene-isatin hybrids as potential anti-tubercular agents against both drug-susceptible and drug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 180: 648–655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2019.07.057>

- Halgren TA, Murphy RB, Friesner RA, Beard HS, Frye LL, Pollard WT, & Banks JL (2004) Glide: a new approach for rapid, accurate docking and scoring. 2. Enrichment factors in database screening. *Journal of medicinal chemistry* 47(7): 1750–1759. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm030644s>
- Hamza HF, Al-Mudhafar MM (2024) Synthesis and characterization of new 5-fluoroisatin- chalcone conjugates with expected antimicrobial activity. *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 33(2): 138–146. <https://doi.org/10.31351/vol33iss2pp138-146>
- Harder E, Damm W, Maple J, Wu C, Reboul M, Xiang JY, Wang L, Lupyán D, Dahlgren MK, Knight JL, Kaus JW (2016) OPLS3: a force field providing broad coverage of drug-like small molecules and proteins. *Journal of chemical theory and computation* 12(1): 281–296. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.5b00864>
- Heaslet H, Harris M, Fahnoe K, Sarver R, Putz H, Chang J, Subramanyam C, Barreiro G and Miller JR (2009) Structural comparison of chromosomal and exogenous dihydrofolate reductase from *Staphylococcus aureus* in complex with the potent inhibitor trimethoprim. *Proteins* 76: 706–717. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.22383>
- Ismail WF, Al-Mudhafar MM, Fadhil AA (2022) Synthesis, characterization of new isatin- ibuprofen derivatives with expected biological activity. *International Journal of Drug Delivery Technology* 12(4): 1560–1565. <https://doi.org/10.25258/ijddt.12.4.13>
- Jarapula R, Gangarapu K, Manda S, Rekulapally S (2016) Synthesis, in vivo anti-inflammatory activity, and molecular docking studies of new isatin derivatives. *International Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 2016(1): 2181027. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/2181027>
- Kamoon RA, Al-Mudhafar MM, Omar TN (2020) Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial evaluation of new azo compounds derived from sulfonamides and isatin schiff base. *International Journal of Drug Delivery Technology* 10: 150–155. <https://doi.org/10.25258/ijddt.10.1.26>
- Khajouei MR, Mohammadi-Farani A, Moradi A, Aliabadi A (2018) Synthesis and evaluation of anticonvulsant activity of (Z)-4-(2-oxoindolin-3-ylideneamino)-N-phenylbenzamide derivatives in mice. *Research in pharmaceutical sciences* 13(3): 262–272. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1735-5362.228956>
- Mohammed H, Leelon A (2021) Synthesis, characterization of isatin dithiocarbamate derivatives with expected biological activities. *International Journal of Drug Delivery Technology* 11(1): 209–212. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23031317>
- Mukhlif MM, Al-Mudhafar MM (2023a) Synthesis, characterization, and preliminary antimicrobial evaluation of new schiff bases and mannich bases of isatin. *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 32(Suppl.): 156–163. <https://doi.org/10.31351/vol32issSuppl.pp156-163>
- Mukhlif M, Al-Mudhafar MM (2023b) Synthesis, characterization of schiff's and mannich bases of 5-fluoroisatin and preliminary antimicrobial evaluation. *Journal of Population Therapeutics and Clinical Pharmacology* 30(13): 381–389. <https://doi.org/10.47750/jptcp.2023.30.13.039>
- Narramore S, Stevenson CE, Maxwell A, Lawson DM, Fishwick CW (2019) New insights into the binding mode of pyridine-3-carboxamide inhibitors of *E. coli* DNA gyrase. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry* 27(16): 3546–3550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2019.06.015>
- Popiolek Ł (2017) Hydrazide-hydrazones as potential antimicrobial agents: overview of the literature since 2010. *Medicinal Chemistry Research* 26: 287–301. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00044-016-1756-y>
- Sabah AA, Al-Rawi MS, Tomma JH (2020) Study the toxicity and anti-cancer activity of some new amic acid and their derivatives of mefenamic acid. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology* 14(1): 642–648. <https://doi.org/10.37506/ijfmt.v14i1.123>
- Sabzi NA, Al-Mudhafar MM (2023) Synthesis, characterization, and preliminary evaluation of antimicrobial activity of imines derived from vanillic acid conjugated to heterocyclic. *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 32(Suppl.): 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.31351/vol32iss-Suppl.pp8-15>
- Sagatova AA, Keniya MV, Wilson RK, Monk BC, Tyndall JDA (2015) Structural insights into binding of the antifungal drug fluconazole to *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* lanosterol 14-demethylase. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 59: 4982–4989. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.00925-15>
- Sahib HA, Mohammed MH (2020) Synthesis and preliminary biological activity evaluation of new N-substituted phthalimide derivatives. *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 29(1): 247–252. <https://doi.org/10.31351/VOL29ISS1PP247-252>
- Selvam P, Chandramohan M, De Clercq E, Witvrouw M, Pannecouque C (2001) Synthesis and anti-HIV activity of 4- [(1, 2-dihydro-2-oxo-3H-indol-3-ylidene) amino]-N (4, 6-dimethyl- 2-pyrimidinyl)-benzene sulfonamide and its derivatives. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 14(4): 313–316. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0928-0987\(01\)00197-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0928-0987(01)00197-x)
- Shakir TH, Al-Mudhafar MM (2020) Synthesis and preliminary antimicrobial evaluation of schiff bases of N-benzyl isatin derivatives. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy* 11(12): 1950–1955. <https://doi.org/10.31838/srp.2020.12.297>
- Sharma M, Prasher P (2023) Synthesis and medicinal applications of fenamic acid derivatives. *Current Organic Chemistry* 27(13): 1132–1142. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1385272827666230914113509>
- Zeeshan S, Naveed M, Khan A, Atiq A, Arif M, Ahmed MN, Kim YS, Khan S (2019) N- pyrazoloyl and N-thiopheneacetyl hydrazone of isatin exhibited potent anti-inflammatory and anti-nociceptive properties through suppression of NF-κB, MAPK and oxidative stress signaling in animal models of inflammation. *Inflammation Research* 68: 613–632. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00011-019-01245-9>
- Zhen X, Peng Z, Zhao S, Han Y, Jin Q, Guan L (2015) Synthesis, potential anticonvulsant and antidepressant effects of 2-(5-methyl-2, 3-dioxindolin-1-yl) acetamide derivatives. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B* 5(4): 343–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsb.2015.01.008>

Supplementary material 1

Data

Authors: Lubna Layth Taha, May Mohammed Jawad Al-Mudhafar
Data type: rar

Explanation note: FT-IR and H-NMR pdf files in two different folders.

Copyright notice: This dataset is made available under the Open Database License (<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0>). The Open Database License (ODbL) is a license agreement intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Dataset while maintaining this same freedom for others, provided that the original source and author(s) are credited.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e143889.suppl1>